

Determination of the Components of the Binary Mixtures of Organic Acids by Vanadium(V) in Perchloric Acid

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The determination of the components of the mixture containing an organic acid quantitatively oxidisable by vanadium(v) in perchloric acid and another organic acid which may or may not be so oxidised by the oxidant, has been described.

The standardised solution of Na(or NH₄)VO₃ in dilute HClO₄ has been used to determine components of the binary mixtures prepared either by combining one non-reducing acid (category A) with a reducing acid (category B) or by combining two acids of category B. The former mixtures gave better results. The standardisation of vanadium(v) solution was effected by standard solutions of one or both of the components of the mixtures.

A few titrimetric methods are available for the determination of the components of binary mixtures of various organic acids¹. Recently a mixture of oxalic and malonic acids has been analysed². From these accounts it is evident that the determination of various types of carboxylic acids in mixtures is interesting. A very simple method for such determination is reported here.

During the iodometric determination of carbohydrates and related compounds^{3,4}, it was anticipated that vanadium(v) in perchloric acid should be a useful reagent for the determination of the components of the binary mixtures of carboxylic acids. Thus, different mixtures prepared from any one of formic, acetic, phenylacetic, glutaric, succinic and benzoic acids (marked as 'Category-A') which do not react with vanadium(v) and any one of tartaric, citric, oxalic and sugar acids (or their calcium salts) like glucuronic, saccharic, gluconic and galactonic acids (marked as 'Category-B') which are affected by the oxidant have been studied. It has been observed that binary mixtures prepared by combining any acids of category-A with another acid of category-B gave accurate results while the mixtures obtained by combining two acids from category-B gave somewhat less accurate results. Since formic acid was one of the final products during the determination of sugars and sugar acids⁴, the mixtures of formic acid and any one of oxalic, citric and tartaric acids were investigated by this method.

Results and Discussion

Fairly accurate results were obtained when the binary mixtures of acids of category-A (not oxidised by vanadate) and category-B (oxidised by vanadate) were analysed. Under the aforementioned experimental conditions, formic acid was found to remain unaffected upto a concentration of about 6%. Oxalic acid was completely oxidised by the boiling oxidant within 15 min and thereafter the titre values remained unaltered. However, in this case, the refluxing for

20 min is recommended, with other acids of category-B the refluxing for 40 min completed the reaction. In method 1, the vanadate solution was standardised each time by the acids of known strength of category-B which is one of the components of the mixture. The method 2 involves prior determinations of the equivalent weights of all the acids of category-B which are then used during calculations. This is more convenient than the method 1 and the results are equally satisfactory. When the total quantities of mixtures (*Q* g) of acids of categories A and B (including formic and acetic acids) were unknown and supplied in aqueous solution, then they could be determined in terms of total equivalents of NaOH consumed by titrimetric method in the usual way followed by the determination of only category-B acids by the vanadium(v) method. But the known volumes of the solutions of binary mixtures of acids of only category-B were evaporated to dryness to determine the total quantities (*Q* g) of the acid, then proceeded in the usual vanadium(v) method to determine each component. In both the cases the errors were within $\pm 2.5\%$. The advantages of the present procedure are that many analyses could be carried out simultaneously within a reasonably short period of time. Also the sharp and stable end-point together with the non-hazardous simple procedure makes this method quite attractive.

Experimental

D-Glucuronic acid, hemicalcium salts of D-gluconic and D-galactonic acids and calcium salt of D-saccharic acid (all Sigma) were dried before use. Formic and acetic acids were standardised titrating a dilute solution against a standard NaOH solution using phenolphthalein as the indicator. Usual precautions of iodometric titrations were followed and double-distilled water (over KMnO₄) was used throughout. All other reagents were of analytical grade (Merck). The acids were dried under reduced pressure for 12 h before use. A solution of Na(or NH₄)VO₃ (0.05 mol) in hot water (200 ml) was cooled and then added to a cold

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF THE BINARY MIXTURES OF ACIDS OF CATEGORY -A* AND -B

Acids of category-A	Amount of category-A acid (Q-B) g : (Found)Taken	Amount of citric acid (B) g : (Found)Taken	Amount of category-A acid (Q-B) g : (Found)Taken	Amount of oxalic acid (B) g : (Found)Taken	Amount of category-A acid (Q-B) g : (Found)Taken	Amount of tartaric acid (B) g : (Found)Taken
I	a) (0.0089) 0.0088	a) (0.0152) 0.0153	a) (0.0241) 0.0242	a) (0.0849) 0.0848	a) (0.0123) 0.0119	a) (0.0283) 0.0287
	b) (0.0167) 0.0169	b) (0.0265) 0.0263	b) (0.0363) 0.0363	b) (0.3927) 0.3927	b) (0.0085) 0.0088	b) (0.0354) m 0.0351
	c) (0.0809) 0.0822	c) (0.0500) 0.0487	c) (0.1408) 0.1453	c) (0.3225) 0.3180	c) (0.0281) 0.0284	c) (0.0569) 0.0566
II	a) (0.0750) 0.0753	a) (0.0215) 0.0212	a) (0.1023) 0.1022	a) (0.0276) 0.0277	a) (0.4090) 0.4088	a) (0.0198) 0.0200
	b) (0.1121) 0.1123	b) (0.0125) 0.0123	b) (0.4087) 0.4088	b) (0.0320) 0.0319	b) (0.8251) 0.8252	b) (0.0376) n 0.0377
	c) (0.8264) 0.8262	c) (0.0240) 0.0242	c) (0.8243) 0.8242	c) (0.0217) 0.0218	c) (0.9580) 0.9584	c) (0.0340) 0.0336
III	a) (0.0488) 0.0486	a) (0.0240) 0.0242	a) (0.0125) 0.0122	a) (0.0141) 0.0144	a) (0.0246) 0.0244	a) (0.0198) 0.0200
	b) (0.0825) 0.0822	b) (0.0234) 0.0237	b) (0.0183) 0.0179	b) (0.0232) 0.0236	b) (0.0493) 0.0498	b) (0.0356) o 0.0351
	c) (0.0748) 0.0743	c) (0.0446) 0.0451	c) (0.0419) 0.0416	c) (0.0276) 0.0279	c) (0.0530) 0.0528	c) (0.0398) 0.0400
IV	a) (0.0320) 0.0318	a) (0.0240) 0.0242	a) (0.0174) 0.0172	a) (0.0142) 0.0144	a) (0.0192) 0.0194	a) (0.0224) 0.0222
	b) (0.0639) 0.0636	b) (0.0234) 0.0237	b) (0.0211) 0.0206	b) (0.0328) 0.0333	b) (0.0288) 0.0286	b) (0.0198) p 0.0200
	c) (0.0587) 0.0582	c) (0.0446) 0.0451	c) (0.0236) 0.0244	c) (0.0440) 0.0432	c) (0.0376) 0.0374	c) (0.0198) 0.0200
V	a) (0.0261) 0.0258	a) (0.0234) 0.0237	a) (0.0645) 0.0638	a) (0.0137) 0.0144	a) (0.0280) 0.0282	a) (0.0292) 0.0290
	b) (0.0477) 0.0485	b) (0.0459) 0.0451	b) (0.0693) 0.0692	b) (0.0276) 0.0277	b) (0.0276) 0.0282	b) (0.0412) q 0.0406
	c) (0.0561) 0.0557	c) (0.0483) 0.0487	c) (0.1209) 0.1210	c) (0.0320) 0.0319	c) (0.0622) 0.0624	c) (0.0374) 0.0372
VI	a) (0.0213) 0.0216	a) (0.0245) 0.0242	a) (0.0393) 0.0394	a) (0.0177) 0.0176	a) (0.0201) 0.0200	a) (0.0394) 0.0395
	b) (0.0227) 0.0224	b) (0.0480) 0.0483	b) (0.0543) 0.0542	b) (0.0276) 0.0277	b) (0.0486) 0.0484	b) (0.0198) r 0.0200
	c) (0.0492) 0.0482	c) (0.0715) 0.0725	c) (0.0507) 0.0502	c) (0.0387) 0.0392	c) (0.0604) 0.0602	c) (0.0198) 0.0200

* (i) I, Formic; II, acetic; III, succinic; IV, glutaric; V, phenylacetic; VI, benzoic.

(ii) Range of Q (g) analysed (error %)	a = 0.0240 – 0.1850 (± 2.6%)	g = 0.0700 – 0.0540 (± 15%)	m = 0.0400 – 0.1250 (± 1.5%)
	b = 0.0800 – 0.8800 (± 1.4%)	h = 0.1250 – 0.8750 (± 2%)	n = 0.4020 – 1.000 (± 1.1%)
	c = 0.0550 – 0.1300 (± 1.2%)	j = 0.0220 – 0.0950 (± 2%)	o = 0.0360 – 0.1000 (± 1.4%)
	d = 0.0460 – 0.1200 (± 1.2%)	j = 0.0250 – 0.0870 (± 1.88%)	p = 0.0360 – 0.0700 (± 1.0%)
	e = 0.0390 – 0.1100 (± 1.2%)	k = 0.0520 – 0.1800 (± 1.3%)	q = 0.0420 – 0.1220 (± 1.4%)
	f = 0.0400 – 0.1320 (± 1.37%)	l = 0.0470 – 0.1000 (± 1.2%)	r = 0.0480 – 0.1100 (± 1%)

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THE COMPONENTS OF THE MIXTURE OF CATEGORY-B ACIDS

(i) Method 1 :					
	Total quantity in mixture (Q) g	Amount of tartaric acid (Q-B) g Taken (Found)	Amount of oxalic acid (B) g Taken (Found)	Amount of saccharic acid (Ca-salt) (Q-B) g Taken (Found)	Amount of galactonic acid (hemicalcium salt) (B) g Taken (Found)
	a) 0.0233	a) 0.0128 (0.0128)	a) 0.0105 (0.0105)	a) 0.0124 (0.0123)	a) 0.0120 (0.0121)
	b) 0.0313	b) 0.0055 (0.0054)	b) 0.0258 (0.0259)	b) 0.0202 (0.0199)	b) 0.0186 (0.0189)
	c) 0.0444	c) 0.0186 (0.0182)	c) 0.0258 (0.0262)	c) 0.0124 (0.0125)	c) 0.0543 (0.0542)
(ii) Method 2 :					
		Amount of oxalic acid (B) g Taken (Found)	Amount of tartaric acid (Q-B) g Taken (Found)		Amount of Ca-salt of glucuronic acid
	a) 0.0580	a) 0.0210 (0.0207)	a) 0.0370 (0.0373)	a) 0.0060 (0.0062)	a) 0.0120 (0.0118)
	b) 0.0646	b) 0.0159 (0.0158)	b) 0.0487 (0.0488)	b) 0.0091 (0.0089)	b) 0.0101 (0.0103)
	c) 0.0661	c) 0.0517 (0.0498)	c) 0.0144 (0.0163)	c) 0.0121 (0.0119)	c) 0.0084 (0.0086)
			Amount of citric acid (Q-B) g Taken (Found)		
	a) 0.0321	a) 0.0218 (0.0214)	a) 0.0103 (0.0107)		
	b) 0.0496	b) 0.0312 (0.0323)	b) 0.0184 (0.0173)		
	c) 0.0563	c) 0.0382 (0.0385)	c) 0.0181 (0.0178)		

solution of HClO_4 (70%; 170 ml) in water (200 ml) and standardised against standard solution of either $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ or the organic reductant which was to be analysed as the unknown sample.

The standardisation of vanadate solution by an acid of category-B was done in the following way. A mixture of oxalic acid solution (2 ml; $10.0260 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$) and the metavanadate solution (30.0 ml) was refluxed for 20 min (40 min for other acids of category-B). The resulting green-blue solution was then cooled to room temperature.

The reflux-condenser was washed with water (10 ml), the washings were added to the reaction mixture and the residual vanadate was determined iodometrically. However, the determinations of the components of the binary mixtures of acids belonging to only category-B were done by two different methods.

According to method 1, the vanadate solution was standardised by both the components separately following the cited method. For calculations, the following working formula was used taking the mixture of oxalic and tartaric acids as the representatives of category-B.

$$\frac{(Q - W'_{\text{ox}})}{W_{\text{T}}} (T_1 - T_2) + \frac{W'_{\text{ox}}}{W_{\text{ox}}} (T_1 - T_3) = (T_1 - T_4)$$

where, Q , W_{T} , W_{ox} and W'_{ox} are the quantities (in g) of the binary mixture, tartaric and oxalic acids used to standardise the vanadate solution, and oxalic acid (as unknown) respectively. T_1 is the volume of thiosulphate (ml) required to titrate V ml of V^V solution and T_2 , T_3 and T_4 are the volumes of thiosulphate (ml) required to titrate the residual vanadate from V ml after the oxidation of W_{T} , W'_{ox} and Q respectively (Table 1). This method of calculation is suitable for any binary mixture consisting of only category-B acids.

In method 2, the following working formula was used :

$$\frac{1000 \times W_{\text{m}}}{E_1} + \frac{1000 (Q - W_{\text{m}})}{E_2} = S_{\text{v}} \frac{T_{\text{im}} - T_{\text{fm}} V_{\text{m}}}{T_{\text{im}}}$$

where, Q g of the mixture contains W g of the first component (equivalent weight E_1) and $(Q - W_{\text{m}})$ g of the second component (equivalent weight E_2). V_{m} is the volume (ml) of vanadate solution taken for the determination of mixture, and T_{im} and T_{fm} are the volumes (ml) of thiosulphate solution required by V_{m} before and after the oxidation of the mixture respectively. The strength S_{v} of the vanadate solution was determined using the following expression :

$$S_{\text{v}} = \frac{1000 T_{\text{i}} W}{V (T_{\text{i}} - T_{\text{f}}) E}$$

in terms of any one of the components where V is the volume (ml) of the vanadate solution added to W g of the component with equivalent weight E ; T_{i} and T_{f} are the volumes (ml) of thiosulphate solutions required before and after the oxidation respectively (Table 1). Sometimes method 1 furnished better results although it was more time-consuming than method 2 as the latter required fewer titrations. The binary mixtures Q (g) of categories A and B were prepared by combining weighed amounts of the components. These solid mixtures could be either directly subjected to determination or dissolved in water and a known volume was taken for the determination by adding excess of standard vanadate and proceeding in the usual way. The amount of acid of category-B can be determined by using the formula,

$$B = \frac{W(z - y)}{(z - x)}$$

where, B is the amount (g) of category-B acid in the A ml of the solution of unknown strength, W (g) is the amount of same acid present in A ml solutions of known strength used for the standardisation of vanadate solution, z , x and y are the volumes (ml) of the thiosulphate solution used to titrate V ml of vanadate solution before the oxidation (blank) and after the oxidation by W and B respectively. The amounts of category-A acids were then determined by difference (Table 1).

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